

A Study on E – Wallets A Mode for Sustainable Development in Banking

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Abstract

Banking is one of the most essential areas in economy. As the economy changes, the development towards each sector changes. Sustainable development in Banking is introduced for the welfare of people and the environment. Sustainable development in banking focuses on two major areas namely, operations and financing of projects. Financing environmental friendly projects will increase sustainability in banking. On the other hand, Operational sustainability can be initiated by reducing the use of cash as printing of cash also leads to carbon foot print. The current era is moving forward to highly digitalized economy and one such foremost technique used to bring operational sustainability is cashless economy. In order for brighter future in technology and development of economy, the government and RBI, on its part, have taken steps like removing the charges for NEFT and RTGS, to encourage the use of digital world. There various medium like UPI application, NEFT, RTGS, debit and credit cards, ECS etc. One such innovation of digital economy is E- wallet. E- wallet is most useful applications in technology used for transferring funds and making payments in safest forms. This article focuses on the Evolution of the E- Wallet and their contributions towards a cashless economy for a growth in economy of our country. Also the implications towards this innovation for sustainable development in Banking Sector.

Keywords: Banking, Digital economy, Sustainable development, E-Wallets.

Introduction

Banking in simple words, is the system of business activity for accepting and safeguarding money owned by other individuals and entities and then lending out money in order to earn profit. As days passed by, the need of computerization was felt in Indian Banking Sector in late 1980's in order to improve customer service, book keeping and MIS reporting. Banks began using Information Technology from the year 1988 where RBI set up a committee headed by Dr. C. Rangarajan. Introduction of computerization gained competition between private and foreign Banks. By introducing newer technologies, banks benefited in several ways. Indian government was keen in introducing Electronic Banking as it results in generating revenue and reducing cost drastically. The topmost agenda for Indian Banks in our present lives is Digitalization. Digitalization is

the process of converting data into digital format through adopting technology. The process of digitalization helped banks in excellent customer service, reduction of costs by using ATM's and cashless transactions through mobile banking, Debit and Credit card payments. One such digital banking is E – wallet.

What is E – wallet?

Wallet is a physical form of storing money and using it for making payments for service received or for buying products. A physical wallet turned into an Electronic form is E – wallet. A wallet which allows the user to store cash and make payments through digital form. Digital wallets is also being used as an alternative payment by many E - business players along with net payments or card based payments.

E – Wallets in India

Post demonetization, growth of E – wallets has increased. With the powers being conferred upon Reserve Bank of India (RBI) for regulating the E- Wallets, under the Payment and Settlement Systems Act, 2007, it has issued Prepaid Payment Instruments (PPI) Master Direction. The PPIs are tools which aim at making payments easier by acting as an intermediary. It also includes financial services. Prior permission should be obtained by companies, which are incorporated and registered under the Companies Act 1956, to operate the payment system. E-Wallet is one among such various PPIs modes available. As on July 2019, 46 companies have been granted license by RBI for offering PPIs. As per RBI guidelines, E – wallets are categorized into three categories:

- Closed E – wallets: This instrument does not permit cash withdrawal or redemption. Eg: OLA cabs create e – wallets for making payments towards purchase of products from their products of services.
- Semi – Closed E – wallets: These wallets can be used for purchase of goods and services at merchant locations with a specific contract with the issuer. Eg: Airtel money.
- Open wallets: These wallets are with financial services like fund transfer at merchant locations and can accept cash withdrawals. Eg: M – Pesa wallet by Vodafone in partnership with ICICI Bank.

Review of Literature

Biswa Ranjan et al (2017) studied about cashless economy and the digitalization of the Indian economy. The benefits and challenges of cashless economy are analyzed in the study. Along with net banking and ATM cards, E-Wallet is listed as one of the best cashless payment option in India.

Nirupam et al (2018) highlights the usage of E-Wallet post demonetization. Since the users were in need of more viable options for digital payments, other than cards and online banking, E-Wallet became a notable mode of transaction. The study also identifies the major players in E-Wallet such as Paytm, Mobiwik, etc.

Amir Sohil et al (2018) explores the working of the E-Wallet in detail. The study also touches the security issue with the storage of cash in the wallet by recovering the information from the server. The study pinpoints safety and traceability of cash as the main advantages of E-Wallet.

Raja Sarkar and Sabyasachi Das (2019) explore the process of digitalization and its impact on the financial transactions in India. The study discusses about the crucial benefits such as discounts and cash back that are passed on to the E-Wallet customer. It also elucidates the factors responsible for the increase in digital payments and the steps taken by government and RBI to digitalize the payment system.

Objectives

1. To study and compare the usage of E-Wallet among various age groups.
2. To identify the level of awareness on E-Wallet.
3. To analyze ways to promote the usage of E-Wallet.

Objective 1: To study and compare the usage of E-Wallet among various age groups

Null Hypothesis (H0): Age group of the respondents have no influence on the usage of E-Wallet.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): Age group of the respondents have influence on the usage of E-Wallet.

T-Test

Table 1.1 One sample statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Age of respondents	134	1.49	.956	.083
Usage of e-wallet	134	.03	.210	.018

Source: Primary data

Table 1.2 One-Sample t- test

Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
					Lower
Age of respondents	18.077	133	.000	1.493	1.33
Usage of e-wallet	1.643	133	.103	.030	-.01

Data Interpretation

The table 1.1 has the 'p' value 0.018 which is less than 0.05 at 95% confidence level. Thus the study proves that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted indicating that Age group of the respondents have influence on the usage of E-Wallet.

Objective 2: To identify the level of awareness on various E-Wallets

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significance difference between Age group of the respondents and the awareness of E-Wallet.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is significance difference between Age group of the respondents and the awareness of E-Wallet.

Table 1.3 Chi-square test

		Awareness of E-wallet		Total
		No	Yes	
Age of respondents	18-25	4	89	93
	26-33	0	29	29
	34-41	0	5	5
	42-49	1	0	1
	Above 50	2	4	6
Total		7	127	134

Source: Primary data

Table 1.4

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.752a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	14.321	4	.006
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.411	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	134		

Most familiar E- Wallet- Paytm

Table 1.5 Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.085a	4	.001
Likelihood Ratio	16.530	4	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.064	1	.003
N of Valid Cases	134		

Data interpretation

Since the ‘p’ value is 0.000, the study proves that it is lesser than 0.05 at 95% confidence level and signifies that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted approving that there is significance difference between Age group of the respondents and the awareness of E-Wallet.

Objective 3: To analyse ways to promote the usage of E-Wallet

Around 95% of the respondents are aware of E-Wallet. This awareness can be positively tapped by providing the users with correct information about the E-wallet. In order to do so, the following steps can be taken:

- A Clear picture regarding the operations should be given to the customer by the banks offering E – wallets. For example ICICI bank offers an E- Wallet know as ‘Pockets’. The website provides clear instruction and FAQs about the same.
- Frequent mails or messages should be sent by the banks for awareness to the customers regarding E- wallets and the offers provided.
- Companies or banks offering E- wallet should provide secure and good server so that it is in a position to process large volume of transactions at one go. During the demonetization, Paytm faced a server breakdown as it was not able to handle the sudden increase in transaction.
- One of the major drawbackscited by the respondents was the security of their data. The customers must provide KYC information such as PAN number and Aadhar number. Along with these crucial numbers, it also seeks the debit/credit card details of the user to transfer money to the E- Wallet. Hence, the company is in a position to provide highly encrypted app and server, to prevent the data from falling into wrong hands.
- Since most of the respondents between the age of 18-25 years are aware of E-Wallets, advertisements through social media can be increased to tap more potential users.
- Cash back and credits are seen as a lucrative option for the E- Wallet users. So the company can have tie up with more merchandise outlets. Puma and Adidas gives up to 50% cash back in Paytm. Ola money gives more credit balance to its users as they increase the usage and balance in the E- Wallet.

Conclusion

As the government laid their emphasis on digitalization, focus turned on the various means to execute it. And the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) launched BHIM in the year 2016. The demonetization of the 1000 and 500 rupees notes, left people with little cash to spend. This pushed them to take up alternate payments methods. E-Wallet was one such alternative where the user need not carry physical cash. The study is based on the primary data collected from 134 respondents. The study showed that younger people are aware of E-Wallet. And it is more used by such younger people. Despite high awareness and usage of E-Wallet, the respondents had expressed their insecurities on E-Wallet. Based on that, study focuses on the various ways to promote them. The one main reason for people not using E-Wallet was the security issue. Adding to this there are other reasons too. First, table 1.5 shows that majority of the respondents use Paytm. Despite that, the negative news about the E- Wallets erodes the customers trust on them. Recently, Paytm mall was in news for ordering an enquiry on their employees. The Paytm employee had joined hands with third parties for creating fake orders. This made sure that the cash back given to select merchandise came back to them. Therefore, Paytm had to rope in Ernst &Young for investigating the fraud. Second, people prefer applications like Google Pay and BHIM which acts as an interface between the payer and payee. There is no need for them to store cash in the E-Wallet. Hence, users find these applications more convenient when compared to E- Wallet. Third, people consider other electronic payment modes like internet banking, etc safer. Fourth, there is no equal awareness about E-Wallet, among the various age groups especially above the age of 41 years. With the ever increasing inflow of smart phone, making the above mentioned age group, use of E-Wallet can be done easily. This would help the digitalization of payment and banking system as well as reduce the Reliance on cash transactions bringing sustainability in the economy.

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